

THE INFLUENCE OF THE HEATING ELEMENT ON RESISTANCE WELDING OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE MATERIALS

D. Stavrov, H. E. N. Bersee, A. Beukers

Production Technology Group, Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Delft University of Technology, Kluyverweg 1, 2629 HS, Delft, The Netherlands

ABSTRACT: A comparative experimental study on the influence of different heating elements on the resistance welding process and performance of the joints is presented. Glass fiber reinforced polyetherimide (GF/PEI) was the material used for manufacturing the welding specimens. Stainless steel mesh and carbon fabric were chosen as the materials for production of heating elements for the investigation. The influence of the temperature and clamping force on the resistance of the heating elements was investigated. The impact of the power level and input energy on the quality of the weld was also studied. The quality of the bond was evaluated by mechanical testing and observing the failure modes. Mechanical lap shear strength tests were performed according to ASTM D 1002 standard. Based on obtained results, optimal processing windows were established for both carbon fiber and metallic heating elements. Finally, the processing windows are compared and discussed.

KEYWORDS: Thermoplastic composite, Resistance welding, GF/PEI, Metallic mesh heating element, Carbon fiber heating element.

INTRODUCTION

Fusion bonding, also known as welding, is considered to be a technique ideally suited for joining thermoplastic composites [1]. It uses the main characteristic of thermoplastics to form the joint, which is the possibility of subsequently melting and cooling of the resin while retaining its properties. Fusion bonding eliminates the well-known drawbacks of the traditional joining techniques, like stress concentration (mechanical fastening) [2] and extensive surface preparation and long curing cycles (adhesive bonding) [3,4]. Additionally, welding offers the possibility of not introducing a foreign material in the joint [2,4]. The welding process can be described as the joining of two parts by fusing their contact interfaces, followed by cooling (consolidating) under pressure, which enables the bond to be made.

From the large amount of available welding techniques, resistance welding is considered to be one of the most promising [5]. The heat to the interface is provided by electrically resistant heating element placed between the welded parts. The main advantages of the resistance welding are very simple, low cost tooling [6] and little or no surface treatment [7].

The heating element plays a key role in the process of resistance welding. It supplies the necessary welding energy to the joint and is one of the main contributors to the joint quality and controllability. The heating element remains trapped in the weld after the welding and as such has an impact on the strength of the joint. This fact also points to the possibility of reprocessing the weld if inspection shows flaws or incomplete bonding [7,8]. Generally speaking, any electrically conducting material can be used as a heating element in resistance welding. However, only two materials appear as a real possibility for application, carbon fiber and metallic mesh. Carbon fiber heating elements were extensively investigated in a number of studies [1,8-10]. Their main advantage is the compatibility with the bonded materials, especially in cases where carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics are welded.

Metallic mesh heating element, on the other hand, although with a number of advantages of its own (uniform temperature distribution, good strength values), was investigated in very few studies [11,12].

The aim of this study was to provide deeper insight into the influence of the heating element on the resistance welding of thermoplastic composites. Carbon fabric and stainless steel mesh were the materials that emerged from the preliminary experiments and were used for producing the heating elements in the investigation. The influence of the type of clamping as well as the clamping force on the resistance of the heating elements was investigated in detail. The resistance of the heating elements at elevated temperature was also monitored. The influence of the heating element on the quality of the weld was evaluated by mechanical testing. Input power and welding time were varied in order to obtain the processing windows of the heating elements.

EXPERIMENTAL

The materials chosen for producing the heating elements for the investigation were stainless steel mesh and carbon fabric. The stainless steel mesh had a wire diameter of 0.2 mm, gap of 0.86 mm and thickness of 0.4 mm. In order to provide a rich resin content in the bonding surface, as well as to prevent the entrapment of air in the mesh, the mesh was impregnated with three resin layers (PEI films). The impregnation process was performed in the hot platen press, where the mesh was co-molded with three 100 μm thick PEI films (ULTEM), which were applied from one side to reduce the air entrapment between the wires. The processing pressure was 1.0 MPa, temperature 330°C and holding time 10 min. The heating elements were subsequently cut in size from the impregnated mesh. Care was taken that the heating elements have the same number of wires in longitudinal direction, so there would be no difference in their resistance. Their edges were not impregnated so that a clean contact with the clamps could be provided.

Fig. 1. The experimental welding set-up

The carbon fiber heating element was produced from a single ply of carbon reinforced PEI prepreg, supplied also by Ten Cate Advanced Composites. The carbon fiber heating element underwent the same production procedure as the laminates. The prepreg ply

was placed between two aluminum plates covered with releasing agent and compression molded at temperature, pressure and holding time of 320°C, 1.5 MPa and 10 min, respectively. The heating elements were cut in size from the consolidated ply. Etching away the matrix from the edges of the heating elements provided clean contact with the clamps. The edges were dipped in a bath of Dichloromethane (CH₂CL₂) for a period of 30 minutes.

The material used in the study was continuous glass fiber reinforced polyetherimide (CF/PEI). The preimpregnated material, supplied by Ten Cate Advanced Composites, the Netherlands, had an 8-harness satin weave configuration and 36 %wt resin content. Six-ply laminates, with dimensions of 220x250 mm, were consolidated in the hot platen press. The stacks of material were placed between two aluminum plates, coated with releasing agent prior to every pressing cycle. The laminates were compression molded at temperature of 320°C and consolidation pressure of 1.0 MPa. The preheating time was 35 min and the holding time was 10 min. The laminates were subsequently cooled down to 170°C while the consolidation pressure was maintained. The final thickness of the laminates was 1.8 mm. Welding specimens were subsequently cut in size and degreased prior to welding.

The experimental set-up is shown in Fig.1. An in-house developed pneumatic press was used to apply homogenous pressure along the welding area and on the clamping device. Separate pressure control of the cylinders provided the opportunity of simultaneously applying different welding and clamping pressures. The power was supplied by an electric transformer with maximum DC output of 45 A and 70 V, with computer controlled switch and electrical parameters. Two blocks of high density fiber (HDF) wood covered with a 0.5 mm thick layer of Teflon were used as heat insulators and support, providing alignment of the specimens.

Resistance welding was performed under constant welding pressure. The power supply automatically maintained constant input power during each welding by regulating the voltage and the current. Welded specimens were 220x195 mm, with an overlap of 12 mm, according to ASTM standard. There was practically no treatment of the laminates and heating elements prior to welding, except for the degreasing of the welding specimens.

Heating Elements	Material Electrical Resistivity (Ω-m)	Testing Results
Copper wires in glass fabric	1.72E-8	Poor heat up
Aluminum rolled mesh	3.7E-8	No heat up, vaporizing during welding
Stainless steel mesh	7.2E-7	Good heat up, no anomalies
Carbon fiber UD tape	E-5	Good heat up, low strength
Carbon fiber fabric	E-5	Good heat up, good temp. distribution

Table 1. Heating elements overview

The resistance experiments were performed in air, with only the heating elements clamped between the clamps. The resistance of the heating elements was calculated using the data from the electrical parameters recorded by the system control.

The quality of the bond was evaluated by mechanical lap shear testing. Lap shear strength tests were performed according to ASTM D 1002. The specimens were cut to the standard geometry with a diamond saw from the welded and compression molded specimens and their edges were slightly polished prior to testing. The tests were performed under standard conditions, temperature of 23°C and relative humidity round 50%. The cross-head speed was 1.3 mm/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A short preliminary investigation was performed to determine the best performing heating elements. Several metallic and carbon fiber materials and configurations have been tested. Copper wires woven into glass fiber fabric, aluminum rolled mesh (normally used as lightning protection in composite aircraft structures) and stainless steel woven mesh were the metallic materials tested and UD tape and carbon fabric were the carbon fiber materials. The materials tested and the summary of the results are listed in Table 1. The copper wires woven in glass fiber fabric did not have sufficient electrical resistance to reach the desired temperature at the maximum settings of the power supply. The aluminum mesh heating element had also very low electrical resistance and evaporated between the electrodes when high current was applied. The stainless steel woven mesh showed none of these shortcomings and was able to reach the desired temperature within the range of the power supply.

Fig. 2. The influence of the clamping pressure on the resistance of CF heating elements

Carbon fiber UD tape produced a very thin heating element that did not add much to the final thickness of the welding overlap, which was an advantage with respect to the loading of the joint. However, the main axial loads act in a direction perpendicular to the direction of the fibers, the worst possible loading case for fiber reinforced composites. A carbon fiber UD heating element introduced a very weak layer in the joint, which resulted in inferior lap shear strength values compared with other heating elements. Furthermore, the fibers of the UD heating elements tended to crack under the clamping loads causing preferential heating and non-homogenous temperature distribution along the weld. Carbon fabric heating element, on the other hand, proved to be rather resilient to the clamping forces. They provided rather uniform temperature profiles along the welds and produced joints with relatively good strengths. Stainless steel mesh and carbon fabric heating elements were the obvious choice of heating elements for the main comparative study.

The resistance of the heating element is one of the most important parameters involved in the process of resistance welding. Its importance results from the close relation between the resistance of the heating element and the welding energy it produces. Therefore it is essential to know the actual resistance of the heating elements used in a particular investigation.

The electrical contact between the clamping device and the heating element has a major impact on the total resistance of the welding system. Since the other external elements of the system (clamps, wires) have known and constant resistances, the contact resistance between the clamps and the heating element determines the amount of input energy that the heating element actually delivers in the welding surface. The clamping force and the type of contact (in case of carbon fiber heating element) have the biggest influence on the contact resistance. The influence of the clamping pressure was investigated by following the total resistance of the system while the clamping pressure was varied. Three ways of removing the matrix from the edges of the carbon fabric heating element were investigated: sanding, burning and etching. The test average values are shown in Fig.2. Sanding the matrix from the edges of the heating element did not produce a satisfactory electrical contact with the clamps. The total resistance was very high with a lot of scatter in the data. The resistance did not achieve its plateau value until the clamping pressure rose to 12 MPa. This was due to the fact that sanding the edges could not provide sufficiently clean fibers and uniformly prepared specimens. Heating elements with the matrix burned away from its edges performed better. The resistance was much lower and rather constant with respect to the clamping load. Its plateau value was achieved at clamping pressure of 4 MPa. There was still a considerable amount of scatter in the results and certain difficulties were experienced in obtaining the desired length of the heating elements. Etching the matrix away from the edges proved to be the most favorable way of preparing the carbon fabric heating elements. It gave the lowest

Fig. 3. The influence of the clamping pressure on the resistance of stainless steel heating element

total resistance and the least scatter in the data. It also achieved the plateau value of the resistance at 4 MPa. The etching procedure provides heating elements with constant clamping resistance. This preparation procedure was used for the rest of the study.

The influence of the clamping force on the resistance of the welding system with stainless steel mesh heating element is shown in Fig.3. Three different measurements are presented. The measurements produced very constant values of the resistance that entered the zone of plateau value at 2 MPa. There was practically no scatter in the results.

The behavior of the resistance at elevated temperatures was also investigated. The relation between the temperature and the resistance for both heating elements is shown in Fig.4. It is clear that these two heating elements belong to different groups of materials with respect to their conductivity. Stainless steel is a typical conductor, with relatively low

Fig. 4. The influence of the temperature on the heating elements resistance

resistance that increases linearly with the rise of the temperature. Carbon fiber on the other hand, is considered as a semi conductor, with electrical properties much closer to those of an insulator. This means that its resistance decreases with the rise of the temperature. The

Fig. 5. Determination of the resistance of the welding system

results showed total loss of 18% of the initial resistance at 400 °C, which is on average $-4.7E-2$ %/°C. The stainless steel heating element gained 30% of the initial resistance in the same temperature interval, which gives an average gain of $8E-2$ %/°C. The described behavior of the resistance should be kept in mind especially in cases when the welding is performed with constant current.

The investigation of the resistance of the heating elements was concluded with the determining the actual resistance of the heating elements and their percentage of the total resistance of the welding system. The resistance of a number of heating elements with same width (12 mm) and different lengths was measured. The results are plotted in Fig.5. The resistance of the system was obtained from the graphs and the resistance of the heating

Fig. 6. Influence of the input energy on LSS for stainless steel heating element

elements was subsequently calculated. The resistance of the stainless steel heating element is 10 times lower than the resistance of the carbon fiber heating element (0.5 Ω as opposed to 5.2 Ω). However, the rest of the welding system had comparative percentages of the total resistance: 6% by the stainless steel and 5% by the carbon fiber heating elements. This indicates once more the big difference in the clamping resistance of the heating elements.

Fig. 7. Influence of the input energy on LSS for carbon fabric heating element

The influence of the heating elements on the quality of the weld was determined by investigating the relation between the input energy and the quality of the weld for both heating elements. The quality of the welds was evaluated by mechanical lap shear strength

testing and visual observation of the failure surface of the tested specimens. The results of the mechanical tests are presented in Fig.6. for stainless steel heating element and in Fig.7. for carbon fabric heating element. The specimens welded with stainless steel heating elements gave better strength values than the carbon fabric heating elements did. Their failure type was predominantly interlaminar, while interfacial failure was more often experienced by carbon fabric welded specimens. This indicates a possibility of strength improvement by specimens welded with carbon fabric heating element (by impregnating the heating element between two resin layers, for example). The strength of the tested specimens along the weld was much more consistent by the specimens welded with stainless steel heating element. Their strength deviation along the weld was not higher than 10%, while the one by specimens welded with carbon fabric heating element mounted to 20%. At high input energies resin flow out of the weld and movement of the heating element was experienced by both heating elements, although less by carbon fabric heating element. However, this did not necessarily influence the final strength of the weld.

Fig. 8. Processing windows

Finally, the processing windows were established for both heating elements, presented in Fig.8. The processing window of the stainless steel heating element is wider, which suggests that stainless steel heating element is less sensitive to the variations of the welding parameters, i.e. welds with satisfactory quality can be produced with a wider range of welding parameters compared to carbon fabric heating element.

CONCLUSIONS

An experimental study on the influence of the heating elements on resistance welding of thermoplastic composites was presented. Stainless steel mesh and carbon fabric emerged from the preliminary study as the most promising materials for producing the heating

elements. The influence of the clamping pressure and temperature on the overall resistance was investigated, as well as the influence of the heating elements on the quality of the weld.

The test results showed that resistance welding with stainless steel mesh heating element is comparatively easier to perform than with carbon fabric heating element. Its edges do not need any preparation prior to welding and good clamping contact is achieved with considerably lower clamping pressure. Furthermore, the clamping contact itself is much better, with lower clamping resistance that produces less energy losses. This was proved by determining the actual resistance of the heating elements and calculating the percentage of losses in the welding system. The behavior of the resistance at elevated temperatures was according to the material properties of the heating elements. The stainless steel heating elements resistance rose at rate of $8E-2 \text{ \%}/^{\circ}\text{C}$, while the resistance of carbon fabric heating element decreased at rate of $-4.7E-2 \text{ \%}/^{\circ}\text{C}$.

The stainless steel heating elements produced welds with better consistency and higher average strength. They were also less sensitive to variations of the welding parameters, which resulted in wider processing window.

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